

FXYP domain containing ion transport regulator 6 (FXYP6): Machine learning discoveries of 2nd order synergy in Meningiomas

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Abstract

Background : FXYP6 belongs to the family of FXYP proteins which appear to associate with Na,K-ATPase α 1- β 1 isozymes. FXYP family consists of small membrane proteins containing a core motif of 35 invariant and conserved amino acids centered on a single transmembrane span. They are expressed in a tissue-specific manner and function by altering the kinetic activity of Na,K-ATPase and it has been noted that FXYP6 expression in humans is mainly in the brain, with highest level of expression found in the prefrontal cortex, amygdala, hypothalamus, and occipital lobe. Meningiomas are the most common intracranial primary neoplasm in adults. Patel et al. [1] analyzed 160 tumors from all 3 World Health Organization (WHO) grades (I through III) using clinical, gene expression, and sequencing data and using unsupervised clustering analysis identified 3 molecular types (A, B, and C) that reliably predicted recurrence. Further, these groups did not directly correlate with the WHO grading system, which classifies more than half of the tumors in the most aggressive molecular type as benign. **Issue** : Increasing evidence point to the fact that meningioma classification and grading, that is based on histopathology does not always accurately predict tumor aggressiveness and recurrence behaviour and knowledge of the underlying biology of the treatment resistant meningiomas and the impact of genetic alterations in these tumors, is lacking. At the current stage more genomic studies are required to unravel the role of other genes and their interactions with other genetic factors. **Resolution** : In a recently published work Sinha [2], a frame work of a search engine was developed which can rank combinations of factors (genes/proteins) in a signaling pathway. Adapting this search engine to the Meningioma dataset, i present here 2nd order combinations of FXYP6, some of which have been known to exist via wet lab experiments, but many are yet to be tested. The reveals combinations might help oncologists/biologists test possible hypotheses that might be the causing factors in meningioma. Further, in my limited grasp, if proven true, the combinations revealed by the search engine might pave way

*ML discoveries of FXYP6 synergy in Meningiomas

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for development of gene based therapies aimed at resolving pathological issues related to meningiomas.

Keywords: FXYD6, Meningioma, Sensitivity analysis, Machine learning.

Contents

1 Introduction	2
1.1 Meningioma	2
1.1.1 World Health Organization (WHO) classification	2
1.1.2 Historical perspective	3
1.1.3 Pathophysiology	4
1.2 FXYD domain containing ion transport regulator 6 (FXYD6)	4
1.3 Insight behind the work	6
1.4 Combinatorial search problem and a possible solution	6
2 Methods	7
2.1 Static data from Patel et al. [1]	7
2.2 Design for static data from Patel et al. [1]	7
2.3 Translating the pipeline into code of execution in R	8
2.4 Regarding biological insight	8
3 Results & Discussion	9
3.1 FXYD6 related synergies	9
3.1.1 FXYD6 - Individual genes	9
4 Conclusion	12
5 References	15

1. Introduction

1.1. Meningioma

Meningiomas are the most common intracranial primary neoplasm in adults. They arise from the arachnoid cap cells. These arachnoid cap cells are specialized cells that make up the arachnoid mater (one of the three protective membranes covering the brain and spinal cord). The arachnoid mater is one of the three meninges. The other two that constitute the meninges are dura mater and pia mater.

1.1.1. World Health Organization (WHO) classification

The meningiomas are classified into three grades by WHO under the Central Nervous System tumours, namely, Grade I (benign), Grade II (atypical) and Grade III (anaplastic/malignant), based on histopathology or subtype (Louis et al. [3]). As of 2021, there

exists 12 histopathological meningioma subtypes according to a mini-review by Torp et al. [4]. They are meningothelial, fibrous, transitional, psammomatous, angiomatous, microcystic, secretory, lymphoplasmacyte-rich, atypical, chordoid, clear cell and anaplastic (malignant) meningioma.

1.1.2. Historical perspective

Czarnetzki et al. [5] investigated a skull that was excavated at Steinheim/Murr (Baden-Württemberg, Germany) and consisted of a well preserved plagiocephalic cranium, with most of the facial skeleton intact. Their results of stratigraphical dating suggested the fossil specimen of *Homo steinheimensis*, was about 3,65,000 years old. In the fossile, they found that several features of the inner cranial table were consistent with a diagnosis of meningioma.

As documented in Okonkwo and Laws Jr [6], in 1614, Felix Plater, Professor of Medicine, issued a case report from the University of Basel on Caspar Bonecurtius, a noble knight stating -

began to lose his mind gradually over a two year period, to such an extent that finally he was completely stupefied and did nothing rationally. He had no desire for food and ate only when forcibly fed. ... Finally after matters had gone on thus for six months, he died.

Further, the autopsy report of Plater stated the following -

a round fleshy tumor, like an acorn. It was hard and full of holes and was as large as a medium-sized apple. It was covered with its own membrane and was entwined with veins. However, it was free of all connections with the matter of the brain, so much so that when it was removed by hand, it left behind a remarkable cavity.

This was the first case in the history that documented a patient with a lesion that was most compatible with a meningioma.

Next, in a contribution by Italian scientists, Paterniti [7] documents the first contribution of Andrea Vacca' Berlinghieri in 1813 in a manuscript *Trattato di Chirurgia Pratica*, which was never published. Its discovery was made accidentally by David Giordano, who referred in detail in an article on surgeon of Pisa in *La chirurgia di Andrea Vacca' Berlinghieri*. *Riv Storia Sci MedNat*. 1927: XVIII (3-4): 75-106. The unpublished manuscript of 488 pages describes that Vacca Berlinhieri proposed and performed a most bold radical operation. After a craniectomy with five or six burr holes on the outskirts of the fungus, the tumor was removed together the dura mater from which it originated, tying the cut vessels.

In 1847, Zanobi Pecchioli, Professor of Clinical Surgery and Operative Medicine at Modena and then at Siena University, published an account of surgeries performed during 16 years, from 1832 to 1847 (16 of the 1524 reported operations involved trephining of the skull). In one of these interventions, he carried out on July 29 1835, in Siena, for the resection of a meningioma, a defined fungus of the duramater. The case was not referred in the literature by Pecchioli but was described by in Pecchioli [8]. Finally, Cushing [9] coined the modern term of "meningioma".

Figure 1: A schematic diagram of different pathways in different meningiomas, as provided by Szulzewsky et al. [12] under CC-BY Attribution 4.0 International license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>)

1.1.3. Pathophysiology

Meningiomas arise from arachnoidal cap cells, most of which are near the vicinity of the venous sinuses, and this is the site of greatest prevalence for meningioma formation. The dural venous sinuses (also called dural/cerebral/cranial sinuses) are venous sinuses (channels) found between the periosteal and meningeal layers of dura mater in the brain. They receive blood from the cerebral veins, and cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) from the subarachnoid space via arachnoid granulations. They mainly empty into the internal jugular vein. Cranial venous sinuses communicate with veins outside the skull through emissary veins. These communications help to keep the pressure of blood in the sinuses constant. (contributors [10] and Pamir et al. [11]) A schematic diagram for different pathways in different meningiomas has been provided in figure 1.

1.2. FXYD domain containing ion transport regulator 6 (FXYD6)

FXYD6 is located at the 11q23.3 (chromosome 11 locus 23.3) and the protein contains 95 amino acids, and can be found in all human tissues except in blood.

Swadner and Rael [13] defined and characterized a gene family of small membrane proteins, represented by phospholemman and the gamma subunit of Na,K-ATPase. In addition to new and more complete cDNA sequence for known family members (including MAT-8, CHIF, and RIC), their findings included two new family members and new splicing variants. They named this gene family was named FXYD (pronounced

fix-id) in recognition of invariant amino acids in its signature motif. They further observed that the abundant proteins are involved in the control of ion transport.

Yamaguchi et al. [14] isolated a cDNA encoding a putative ion channel protein from a rat hippocampus library. Terming this gene phosphohippolin (PHP), they observed that it contained 318 bp open reading frame encoding a single transmembrane protein with a 5' signal peptide region and the deduced amino acid sequence shared 48.1% homology with phospholemman (PLM). While searching the expression sequence tag database (dEST) they located a mouse (AA521976) and human (AA209241) PHP gene homologues. Their tissue distribution studies of Php mRNA showed its abundant expression in rat brain and kidney, and in the brain, they found its high expression in hippocampus and cerebellum.

In a review, Crambert and Geering [15] state that - *Maintenance of the Na⁺ and K⁺ gradients between the intra/extra-cellular milieus of animal cells is a requirement for basic cellular homeostasis and for functions of specialized tissues. The Na,K-ATPase, an oligomeric P-type adenosine triphosphatase (ATPase), is composed of a catalytic α subunit and a regulatory β subunit and is the main player that fulfils these tasks. A variety of regulatory mechanisms are necessary to guarantee appropriate Na,K-ATPase expression and activity adapted to changing physiological demands. Recently, a regulatory mechanism was defined that is mediated by interaction of Na,K-ATPase with small proteins of the FXYD family, which possess a single transmembrane domain and so far have been considered as channels or regulators of ion channels. Phospholemman (FXYD1 or PLM above) in heart and skeletal muscle, the γ subunit of Na,K-ATPase (FXYD2) and corticosteroid hormone-induced factor (FXYD4, also known as CHIF) in the kidney, and FXYD7 in the brain associate preferentially with the widely expressed Na,K-ATPase α 1- β 1 isozyme and modulate its transport activity in a way that conforms to tissue-specific requirements.* The mammalian FXYD proteins FXYD-1-to-7 show tissue-specific distribution and in a review, Crambert and Geering [15] cover the basic mechanics of FXYD proteins.

The deduced amino acid sequence of PHP comprises 93 residues with a core motif of FXYD and a single transmembrane domain. This indicates that PHP belongs to FXYD6 subfamily of the seven FXYD subfamilies (FXYD-1-to-7). In this regard, Kadowaki et al. [16] raised and purified polyclonal antibodies against the carboxyl-terminal sequence of rat PHP. They observed spatial expression of the PHP protein in the neuronal fibers of the medial part of lateral habenula nucleus, thalamus, hypothalamus, stria terminalis, zona incerta, amygdaloid body and cingulum, olfactory bulb, hippocampus, cerebral cortex and cerebellum. Further, they identified a unique PHP distribution in the cerebellum, with a predominant expression pattern in the granule layer of lobules VI-IX of the posterior lobe. Their findings suggested that PHP might play an important role in the excitability of neurons in the central nervous system during postnatal development, as well as those in the adult brain.

Previous linkage analyses of families with multiple cases of schizophrenia have confirmed the involvement of the chromosome 11q22-24 region in the etiology of schizophrenia, with LOD scores of 3.4 and 3.1. Choudhury et al. [17] reported the fine mapping of a susceptibility gene in the 11q22-24 region, based on University College London (UCL) sample of 496 cases and 488 supernormal controls. They then confirmed the results by the study of an Aberdeen sample consisting of 858 cases and

591 controls (for a total of 2,433 individuals: 1,354 with schizophrenia and 1,079 controls). They observed that 7 microsatellite or single-nucleotide polymorphism (SNP) markers localized within or near the FXVD6 gene and showed empirically significant allelic associations with schizophrenia in the UCL sample. In their study, they found several haplotypes associated with schizophrenia and observed that Hap-F21 haplotype showed significant association with schizophrenia in the Aberdeen sample. The FXVD6 gene encodes PHP protein which is highly expressed in regions of the brain thought to be involved in schizophrenia. They think that etiological base-pair changes in FXVD6 or in associated promoter/control regions are likely to cause abnormal function or expression of PHP and to increase genetic susceptibility to schizophrenia.

Many of the different synergies represented as combinations of genes/proteins have been experimentally tested and published. However, there are combinations that have yet to be explored. I address the problem of identifying these unexplored combinations via use of a machine learning based search engine in the next section.

1.3. Insight behind the work

Across all search engines has the fundamental principle remains the same i.e to capture the pattern available in the data and based on that pattern, rank a list of queries. Different algorithms can be applied, however if the fundamental pattern is captured accurately, then the rankings will remain approximately the same, with slight variations, across the different kinds of search engines used. I use one search engine, however, vary the way the patterns are captured via use of different sensitivity methods. Each sensitivity method uses a different flavour/mathematical formulation to compute the sensitivity indices to estimate the influence of the involved factors. These involved factors are genes that play a role in cell biology, in the above research. The insight is that all methods will capture the sensitivity of the involved factors based on their recorded regulations and the search engine will rank the combination of factors based on these sensitivity indices. Since the role of involved factors are captured properly, the search engine will give appropriate rankings to the combinations, thus capturing which gene combinations might be playing significantly in a biological phenomena. The above work shows rankings for experimentally confirmed combinations as well as unexplored/untested combinations. These rankings are not just numbers. They point to the existence of biological synergy in the form of gene combinations, whether tested in wet lab or unexplored till now. Finally, the findings suggest that the rankings are conserved across the different sensitivity methods used.

1.4. Combinatorial search problem and a possible solution

In a recently published work Sinha [2], a frame work of a search engine was developed which can rank combinations of factors (genes/proteins) in a signaling pathway. The work uses SVM package by Joachims [18] in https://www.cs.cornell.edu/people/tj/svm_light/svm_rank.html. I use the adaptation to rank 2^{nd} order gene combinations. The sensitivity package by Pujol et al. [19] was used to develop the search engine pipeline. The current research uses the Hilbert Schmidt Independence

Criterion (HSIC) and SOBOL method, implemented in the sensitivity package mentioned above. I use three different kernels under the HSIC method namely, • laplace, • linear and • rbf. For SOBOL method, I use • sobol-2002, and • sobol-jansen. Each of these variants or kernels have been implemented in the sensitivity package and option has been provided in the search engine code to generate the rankings for a particular gene, using a choice of a kernel/variant at a time. Technical details about the variants and kernels can be found in references cited in Pujol et al. [19].

2. Methods

2.1. Static data from Patel et al. [1]

Patel et al. [1] analyzed 160 meningioma samples from 140 patients, and according to the WHO histopathological classification system for meningioma, they found 121 tumors were of grade I (benign), 32 were of grade II (atypical), and 7 were of grade III (malignant). To determine whether meningiomas could be differentiated based on gene expression profiles, they used principal component analysis (PCA) on a discovery set of 97 tumors (i.e 77 WHO grade I and 20 WHO grade II). Next, they employed nonnegative matrix factorization (NMF) clustering (a unsupervised machine-learning approach) for $k = 2$ to $k = 7$ using the 1,500 genes that varied most among the tumor samples. They report that after 1,000 iterations, 3 clusters ($k = 3$) emerged as providing the best fit as determined by the consensus membership, cophenetic, and silhouette scores. They evaluated the cluster significance of the 3 subtypes using SigClust (Huang et al. [20]) and observed statistical significance between cluster boundaries, which exhibited significant differences in WHO grade representation.

2.2. Design for static data from Patel et al. [1]

The procedure begins with the listing of all C_k^n combinations for k number of genes from a total of n genes. Here n can be the choice of the biologist. k is ≥ 2 and $\leq (n - 1)$. Each of the combination of order k represent a unique set of interaction between the involved genetic factors. Since the sensitivity analysis methods require a sample for a particular observation, a steep gaussian distribution was generated with a jitter (noise) added to the deviation from the reported point measurement of 0.005. In this experiment, the distribution contained 10 measurements (including the point of measurement under consideration). This is repeated for each point of measurement.

To have an averaged ranking, the experiment was designed to run for 25 iterations. In each iteration, the datasets are combined in a specified format which go as input as per the requirement of a particular sensitivity analysis method. Thus for each p^{th} combination in C_k^n combinations, the dataset is prepared in a required format. Details of formatting the data have not been presented in the article to maintain the fluidity and brevity. Interested readers can find examples of forming the data in the sensitivity analysis package in R. Sensitivity analysis and its relevance in systems biology have been covered in a recently published article by Sinha [21], which forms the foundation for this work. After the data has been transformed, vectorized programming is

employed for density based sensitivity analysis and looping is employed for variance based sensitivity analysis to compute the required sensitivity indices for each of the p combinations.

After the above sensitivity indices have been stored for each of the p^{th} combination, for a chosen sensitivity analysis method, the next step in the design of experiment is conducted. Here, the indices are averaged per combination to have a mean index value. These index values form the discriminative features for a particular combination. For a k^{th} order combination, a vector of k elements or indices forms a feature vector. Thus for C_k^n combinations there will be C_k^n vectors, each containing k elements. Next, SVM_{learn}^{Rank} Joachims [18] is used to generate a model on default value C value of 20. In the current experiment on toy model C value has not been tuned. The training set helps in the generation of the model as the different gene combinations are numbered in order which are used as rank indices. The model is then used to generate score on the observations in the testing set using the $SVM_{classify}^{Rank}$ Joachims [18]. This is followed by sorting of these scores along with the rank indices already assigned to the gene combinations. The end result is a sorted order of the gene combinations based on the ranking score learned by the SVM^{Rank} algorithm.

Note that the following is the order in which the files should be executed in R Team [22], in order, for obtaining the desired results (Note that the code will not be explained here) - • use source("extractMeningiomadata.R") • use source("manuscript-2-2.R") • use source("SVMRank-Results-S-mean.R").

2.3. Translating the pipeline into code of execution in R

The execution begins by some preprocessing of the file containing the information regarding the down regulated genes via `source("extractMeningiomadata.R")`. The library containing the sensitivity analysis methods is then loaded in the interface using the command `library(sensitivity)` (Note - this package can be downloaded for free from <https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/sensitivity/index.html>). Next a gaussian distribution for a particular transcript level for a gene is generated to have a sample. This is needed in the computation of sensitivity index for that particular gene. A gene of particular choice is selected (in blue) and the choice of the combination is made (here $k = 2$). Later a kernel is used (here rbf for HSIC method). 25 different indices are generated which help in generating aggregate rank using these 25 indices. The Support vector ranking algorithm is employed to generate the scores for different combinations and these scores are then sorted out. This is done using the command `source("SVMRank - Results - S - mean.R")`. A file is generated that contains the combinations in increasing order of influence. Note that 1 means lowest rank and vice versa, for 2^{nd} order combinations for any gene using a particular density based sensitivity index.

2.4. Regarding biological insight

For the recorded gene expression values, the sensitivity indices are computed. The search engine uses the kernel based density method. The kernel method takes the data, that is in a lower dimensional plane and projects it to a higher dimensional plane,

with an idea that in a higher dimensional place, there exists a dot product between the projected data. To simply state, the idea is that in a higher dimensional plane the nonlinearities between the data (in lower dimensional plane) will be captured and the data may be segregated from each other via a hyperplane. So, irrespective of the method used to measure the gene expression values, if the measurements capture biological information (to whatever extent they can), then the kernel method will be able to capture the nonlinearities/synergies, if existing and allow the sensitivity analysis method (here density based method) to estimate the strength of influence of each of the factors. Based on the sensitivity indices of combinations of a particular order, the search engine ranks the combinations. Details of search engine are provided in the published work in Sinha [2].

It is important to note that the search engine will not give insight about the mechanism of synergy between the components of a combination. However, if the synergy exists between components of an unexplored/untested combination, then the sensitivity indices will capture the influence of these components taken together (which form a combination of interest) and will rank the combination appropriately. These rankings provide insight about which combination a biologist/oncologist might want to test in a forest of combinations for a given scenario in a cell (whether normal or pathological).

3. Results & Discussion

3.1. FXYD6 related synergies

Note - FXYD6 was found to be upregulated in Type A. Upregulation was defined as Type logFC to be > 1 and $FDR \leq 0.001$, in Patel et al. [1]. Also, sorting of scores by the machine learning algorithm were done in ascending order, i.e - top is lowest in ranking. A total of 307 ^{2nd} order combinations of FXYD6 were recorded.

3.1.1. FXYD6 - Individual genes

The following genes were found to show high rankings along with FXYD6 - USH1 protein network component harmonin (USH1C), V-set and immunoglobulin domain containing 2 (VSIG2), mucolipin TRP cation channel 3 (MCOLN3), ST6 N-acetylgalactosaminide alpha-2,6-sialyltransferase 2 (ST6GALNAC2), calpain 6 (CAPN6), ATP binding cassette subfamily B member 1 (ABCB1), parathyroid hormone like hormone (PTH1LH), neurotensin receptor 1 (NTSR1), junctophilin 1 (JPH1), cordon-bleu WH2 repeat protein (COBL), interleukin 1 receptor like 1 (IL1RL1), 24-dehydrocholesterol reductase (DHCR24), tetraspanin 1 (TSPAN1), phospholipid phosphatase related 4 (PLPPR4), myelin regulatory factor (MYRF), SRY-box transcription factor 9 (SOX9), kallikrein related peptidase 10 (KLK10), kallikrein related peptidase 8 (KLK8), proline rich and Gla domain 3 (PRRG3), serine/threonine kinase 26 (STK26), BICD family like cargo adaptor 1 (BICDL1), p21 (RAC1) activated kinase 6 (PAK6), GIPC PDZ domain containing family member 2 (GIPC2), HECT, C2 and WW domain containing E3 ubiquitin protein ligase 2 (HECW2), HECT and RLD domain containing E3 ubiquitin protein ligase 5 (HERC5), RasGEF domain family member 1B (RASGEF1B),

cyclin dependent kinase like 2 (CDKL2), epidermal growth factor (EGF), shisa like 1 (KIAA1644), PILR alpha associated neural protein (PIANP), collagen type II alpha 1 chain (COL2A1), SLAIN motif family member 1 (SLAIN1), MAM domain containing glycosylphosphatidylinositol anchor 2 (MDGA2), ring finger protein 157 (RNF157), solute carrier family 47 member 1 (SLC47A1), PR/SET domain 16 (PRDM16), solute carrier family 44 member 3 (SLC44A3), cellular retinoic acid binding protein 2 (CRABP2), sushi domain containing 4 (SUSD4), HHIP like 2 (HHIPL2), coiled-coil domain containing 150 (CCDC150), atypical chemokine receptor 3 (ACKR3), immunoglobulin superfamily member 11 (IGSF11), coiled-coil domain 39 molecular ruler complex subunit (CCDC39), serine protease 35 (PRSS35), astrotactin 2 (ASTN2), coiled-coil domain containing 81 (CCDC81), glycoprotein hormone subunit alpha 2 (GPHA2), cadherin 8 (CDH8), family with sequence similarity 124 member A (FAM124A), coiled-coil domain containing 3 (CCDC3), inter-alpha-trypsin inhibitor heavy chain 2 (ITIH2), calcium voltage-gated channel auxiliary subunit alpha2delta 1 (CACNA2D1), serine and arginine rich splicing factor 12 (SRSF12), neural cell adhesion molecule 2 (NCAM2), solute carrier family 26 member 2 (SLC26A2), chloride intracellular channel 2 (CLIC2), glutamate receptor interacting protein 1 (GRIP1), SH3 domain containing ring finger 2 (SH3RF2), STEAP2 metalloredoxase (STEAP2), grainyhead like transcription factor 3 (GRHL3), nucleophosmin/nucleoplasmin 2 (NPM2), chloride intracellular channel 6 (CLIC6), actin alpha cardiac muscle 1 (ACTC1), angiotensin I converting enzyme (ACE), spondin 2 (SPON2), C3 and PZP like alpha-2-macroglobulin domain containing 8 (CPAMD8), cholinergic receptor nicotinic beta 2 subunit (CHRN2), cytochrome P450 family 3 subfamily A member 4 (CYP3A4), NHS like 3 (NHSL3 / KIAA1 MYO1A 522), AKNA domain containing 1 (AKNAD1), Rho guanine nucleotide exchange factor 3 (ARHGEF3), sphingomyelin synthase 2 (SGMS2), solute carrier family 9 member B2 (SLC9B2), FHF complex subunit HOOK interacting protein 1A (FAM160A1), ankyrin repeat domain 33B (ANKRD33B), STEAP family member 1 (STEAP1), adenylate cyclase 1 (ADCY1), lysine demethylase 1B (KDM1B), transient receptor potential cation channel subfamily V member 6 (TRPV6), aquaporin 3 (Gill blood group) (AQP3), phytanoyl-CoA 2-hydroxylase interacting protein like (PHYHIPL), protein phosphatase 1 regulatory subunit 36 (PPP1R36), calcium voltage-gated channel auxiliary subunit beta 2 (CACNB2), serine peptidase inhibitor, Kunitz type 1 (SPINT1), sodium voltage-gated channel beta subunit 3 (SCN3B), ubiquitin specific peptidase 54 (USP54), serpin family B member 8 (SERPINB8), pleckstrin homology domain containing A7 (PLEKHA7), alanyl aminopeptidase, membrane (ANPEP), myosin IA (MYO1A), small G protein signaling modulator 1 (SGSM1), glycerol-3-phosphate dehydrogenase 1 (GPD1), dynein axonemal assembly factor 3 (DNAAF3), phospholipase A and acyltransferase 5 (PLAAT5 / HRASLS5), bradykinin receptor B2 (BDKRB2), neuronal vesicle trafficking associated 1 (NSG1), RAB3B, member RAS oncogene family (RAB3B), OTU deubiquitinase 7A (OTUD7A), DLG associated protein 1 (DLGAP1), CDC42 binding protein kinase gamma (CDC42BPG), anoctamin 5 (ANO5), cilia and flagella associated protein 46 (CFAP46), angiotensin like 7 (ANGPTL7), interferon stimulated exonuclease gene 20 (ISG20), membrane bound glycerophospholipid O-acyltransferase 1 (MBOAT1), tryptase alpha/beta 1 (TPSAB1), serine palmitoyltransferase long chain base subunit 3 (SPTLC3), bisphosphoglycerate mutase (BPGM), regulator of calcineurin 2 (RCAN2), radial spoke

head component 9 (RSPH9), carboxylesterase 4A (CES4A), ciliary microtubule associated protein 3 (PIFO), solute carrier organic anion transporter family member 2A1 (SLCO2A1), solute carrier family 35 member G1 (SLC35G1), myosin ID (MYO1D), family with sequence similarity 91 member A1 (FAM91A1), potassium voltage-gated channel subfamily A member 2 (KCNA2), LRRN4 C-terminal like (LRRN4CL), G protein-coupled receptor 4 (GPR4), endoplasmic reticulum to nucleus signaling 1 (ERN1), transmembrane protein 125 (TMEM125), WSC domain containing 1 (WSCD1), transmembrane protein 30B (TMEM30B), synemin (SYNM), calpain 12 (CAPN12), receptor interacting serine/threonine kinase 4 (RIPK4), family with sequence similarity 162 member B (FAM162B), coiled-coil serine rich protein 1 (CCSER1), brain expressed X-linked 5 (BEX5), oxysterol binding protein 2 (OSBP2), MAF bZIP transcription factor F (MAFF), transcobalamin 2 (TCN2), piccolo presynaptic cytomatrix protein (PCLO), insulin induced gene 1 (INSIG1), NF2, moesin-ezrin-radixin like (MERLIN) tumor suppressor (NF2), natural killer cell cytotoxicity receptor 3 ligand 1 (NCR3LG1), family with sequence similarity 78 member B (FAM78B), FAT atypical cadherin 4 (FAT4), solute carrier family 6 member 9 (SLC6A9), laminin subunit beta 3 (LAMB3), tryptase beta 2 (TPSB2), ectonucleotide pyrophosphatase/phosphodiesterase 1 (ENPP1), AFDN divergent transcript (AFDN-DT), SH3 domain binding glutamate rich protein like 2 (SH3BGRL2), ankyrin repeat domain 35 (ANKRD35), sterol regulatory element binding transcription factor 2 (SREBF2), collagen type XV alpha 1 chain (COL15A1), family with sequence similarity 120A2, pseudogene (FAM120A2P / C9orf129).

Using the adaptation of the above mentioned search engine, I was able to tabulate 2nd order combinations of FXYD6 with these genes, that were reported to be upregulated in Patel et al. [1].

Table 1 and 2 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 3 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 1 and 2.

One can also interpret the results of the table 1 and 2 graphically, with the following influences -

- Individual members w.r.t FXYD6 with FXYD6 – > USH1C / VSIG2 / MCOLN3 / ST6GALNAC2 / CAPN6 / ABCB1 / PTHLH / NTSR1 / JPH1 / COBL / IL1RL1 / DHCR24 / TSPAN1 / PLPPR4 / MYRF / SOX9 / KLK10 / KLK8 / PRRG3 / STK26 / BICDL1 / PAK6 / GIPC2 / HECW2 / HERC5 / RASGEF1B / CDKL2 / EGF / KIAA1644 / PIANP / COL2A1 / SLAIN1 / MDGA2 / RNF157 / SLC47A1 / PRDM16 / SLC44A3 / CRABP2 / SUSD4 / HHIPL2 / CCDC150 / IGSF11 / CCDC39 / PRSS35 / ASTN2 / GPHA2 / CDH8 / FAM124A / CCDC3 / ITIH2 / CACNA2D1 / SRSF12 / NCAM2 / SLC26A2 / CLIC2 / GRIP1 / SH3RF2 / STEAP2 / GRHL3 / NPM2 / CLIC6 / ACTC1 / ACE / SPON2 / CPAMD8 / CHRNB2 / CYP3A4 / KIAA1522 / AKNAD1 / ARHGEF3 / SGMS2 / SLC9B2 / FAM160A1 / ANKRD33B / STEAP1 / ADCY1 / KDM1B / TRPV6 / AQP3 / PHYHIPL / PPP1R36 / CACNB2 / SPINT1 / SCN3B / USP54 / SERPINB8 / PLEKHA7 / ANPEP / MYO1A / SGSM1 / GPD1 / DNAAF3 / HRASLS5 / BDKRB2 / NSG1 / RAB3B / OTUD7A / DLGAP1 / CDC42BPG / ANO5 / CFAP46 / ANGPTL7 / ISG20 / MBOAT1 / TPSAB1 / SPTLC3 / BPGM / RCAN2 / RSPH9 / CES4A / PIFO / SLCO2A1 / SLC35G1 / MYO1D / FAM91A1 / KCNA2 / LRRN4CL / GPR4 / ERN1 / TMEM125 / WSCD1 / TMEM30B / SYNM / CAPN12 / RIPK4 / FAM162B / CCSER1 / BEX5 / OSBP2 / MAFF / TCN2 / PCLO / INSIG1 / NF2 / NCR3LG1 / FAM78B / FAT4 / SLC6A9 / LAMB3 / TPSB2 / ENPP1 / AFDN-

RANKING INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS VS FXYD6									
RANKING OF INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS W.R.T FXYD6									
	laplace	linear	rbf	jansen		laplace	linear	rbf	jansen
USHIC - FXYD6	217	275	206	26	VSIG2 - FXYD6	163	218	162	13
MCOLN3 - FXYD6	246	202	184	32	ST6GALNAC2 - FXYD6	155	124	199	264
CAPN6 - FXYD6	164	157	153	25	ABCB1 - FXYD6	177	231	164	259
PTHLH - FXYD6	150	199	141	304	NTSR1 - FXYD6	195	183	194	31
JPH1 - FXYD6	156	203	139	2	COBL - FXYD6	220	213	180	10
ILIRL1 - FXYD6	167	182	209	67	DHCR24 - FXYD6	143	194	109	260
TSPAN1 - FXYD6	199	205	151	29	PLPPR4 - FXYD6	180	296	227	171
MYRF - FXYD6	208	154	145	35	SOX9 - FXYD6	200	187	230	292
KLK10 - FXYD6	221	145	250	14	KLK8 - FXYD6	293	223	218	116
PRRG3 - FXYD6	186	200	191	69	STK26 - FXYD6	281	169	128	284
BICDL1 - FXYD6	154	209	97	306	PAK6 - FXYD6	300	300	276	179
GIPC2 - FXYD6	165	208	279	221	HECW2 - FXYD6	230	177	161	236
HERC5 - FXYD6	260	282	253	171	RASGEF1B - FXYD6	257	221	304	149
CDKL2 - FXYD6	245	220	233	238	EGF - FXYD6	196	245	269	48
KIAA1644 - FXYD6	149	267	272	68	PIANP - FXYD6	185	144	144	85
COL2A1 - FXYD6	190	237	150	278	SLAIN1 - FXYD6	229	292	290	162
MDGA2 - FXYD6	63	159	138	299	RNF157 - FXYD6	289	273	203	169
SLC47A1 - FXYD6	189	289	252	159	PRDM16 - FXYD6	231	167	267	70
SLC44A3 - FXYD6	280	232	255	206	CRABP2 - FXYD6	283	251	224	217
SUSD4 - FXYD6	175	138	101	276	HHIPL2 - FXYD6	179	166	115	303
CCDC150 - FXYD6	203	256	202	89	IGSF11 - FXYD6	173	295	261	114
CCDC39 - FXYD6	271	261	307	132	PRSS35 - FXYD6	209	283	294	129
ASTN2 - FXYD6	193	128	190	121	GPHA2 - FXYD6	222	294	305	174
CDH8 - FXYD6	135	190	286	270	FAM124A - FXYD6	169	207	183	286
CCDC3 - FXYD6	259	184	200	258	ITIH2 - FXYD6	235	168	212	57
CACNA2D1 - FXYD6	267	262	193	119	SRSF12 - FXYD6	302	211	208	222
NCAM2 - FXYD6	247	288	160	230	SLC26A2 - FXYD6	285	214	249	249
CLIC2 - FXYD6	239	248	238	141	GRIP1 - FXYD6	191	279	259	203
SH3RF2 - FXYD6	219	290	197	193	STEAP2 - FXYD6	240	191	222	263
GRHL3 - FXYD6	103	158	266	272	NPM2 - FXYD6	270	224	258	86
CLIC6 - FXYD6	215	171	188	234	ACTC1 - FXYD6	254	280	260	252
ACE - FXYD6	261	269	288	168	SPON2 - FXYD6	234	186	270	205
CPAMD8 - FXYD6	241	192	263	273	CHRN2 - FXYD6	237	229	248	183
CYP3A4 - FXYD6	244	243	229	78	KIAA1522 - FXYD6	296	266	298	166
AKNAD1 - FXYD6	127	173	169	282	ARHGEF3 - FXYD6	214	235	273	117
SGMS2 - FXYD6	301	272	204	170	SLC9B2 - FXYD6	307	287	264	223
FAM160A1 - FXYD6	224	293	282	226	ANKRD33B - FXYD6	291	219	192	250
STEAP1 - FXYD6	166	254	171	208	ADCY1 - FXYD6	275	291	293	106

Table 1: 2nd order interaction ranking between FXYD6 VS Individual members.

DT / SH3BGRL2 / ANKRD35 / SREBF2 / COL15A1 / C9orf129.

4. Conclusion

Presented here are a range of multiple synergistic FXYD6 2nd order combinations that were ranked via a machine learning based search engine. Via majority voting across the ranking methods, it was possible to find plausible unexplored synergistic combinations of FXYD6-X that might be prevalent in meningioma.

RANKING INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS VS FXYD6									
RANKING OF INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS W.R.T FXYD6									
	laplace	linear	rbf	jansen		laplace	linear	rbf	jansen
KDM1B - FXYD6	278	176	262	82	TRPV6 - FXYD6	251	238	242	189
AQP3 - FXYD6	62	172	152	216	PHYHIPL - FXYD6	176	281	186	112
PPP1R36 - FXYD6	226	230	239	94	CACNB2 - FXYD6	292	286	243	229
SPINT1 - FXYD6	187	301	300	178	SCN3B - FXYD6	288	264	296	101
USP54 - FXYD6	276	304	201	123	SERPINB8 - FXYD6	268	265	291	175
PLEKHA7 - FXYD6	265	307	277	190	ANPEP - FXYD6	305	297	217	198
MYO1A - FXYD6	282	250	211	73	SGSM1 - FXYD6	294	299	285	199
GPD1 - FXYD6	252	115	136	291	DNAAF3 - FXYD6	238	147	232	77
HRASLS5 - FXYD6	106	153	147	305	BDKRB2 - FXYD6	161	136	135	298
NSG1 - FXYD6	211	233	275	104	RAB3B - FXYD6	228	185	166	74
OTUD7A - FXYD6	227	225	226	214	DLGAP1 - FXYD6	284	179	216	281
CDC42BPG - FXYD6	253	244	143	113	ANO5 - FXYD6	279	134	185	255
CFAP46 - FXYD6	299	277	302	173	ANGPTL7 - FXYD6	286	226	205	135
ISG20 - FXYD6	233	271	292	177	MBOAT1 - FXYD6	216	193	287	246
TPSAB1 - FXYD6	178	152	181	283	SPTLC3 - FXYD6	264	259	254	130
BPGM - FXYD6	304	306	237	207	RCAN2 - FXYD6	250	270	299	158
RSPH9 - FXYD6	256	247	281	134	CES4A - FXYD6	274	189	246	167
PIFO - FXYD6	194	268	234	124	SLCO2A1 - FXYD6	266	242	215	165
SLC35G1 - FXYD6	243	276	213	120	MYO1D - FXYD6	153	120	268	257
FAM91A1 - FXYD6	295	278	306	185	KCNA2 - FXYD6	272	285	271	145
LRRN4CL - FXYD6	273	258	265	71	GPR4 - FXYD6	223	274	121	188
ERN1 - FXYD6	277	305	303	184	TMEM125 - FXYD6	198	222	179	126
WSCD1 - FXYD6	298	196	221	213	TMEM30B - FXYD6	218	206	228	224
SYNM - FXYD6	168	216	149	54	CAPN12 - FXYD6	290	246	295	138
RIPK4 - FXYD6	171	198	167	34	FAM162B - FXYD6	162	160	165	108
CCSER1 - FXYD6	170	257	214	242	BEX5 - FXYD6	232	156	146	33
OSBP2 - FXYD6	205	195	107	274	MAFF - FXYD6	225	217	236	125
TCN2 - FXYD6	249	252	231	211	PCLO - FXYD6	151	40	178	300
INSIG1 - FXYD6	262	298	235	191	NF2 - FXYD6	197	175	257	265
NCR3LG1 - FXYD6	269	303	297	220	FAM78B - FXYD6	306	241	284	92
FAT4 - FXYD6	188	228	241	83	SLC6A9 - FXYD6	207	215	220	231
LAMB3 - FXYD6	183	255	247	248	TPSB2 - FXYD6	159	188	182	137
ENPP1 - FXYD6	236	141	210	66	AFDN-DT - FXYD6	303	284	301	122
SH3BGRL2 - FXYD6	287	239	289	227	ANKRD35 - FXYD6	181	240	240	160
SREBF2 - FXYD6	201	201	225	209	COL15A1 - FXYD6	263	302	283	163
C9orf129 - FXYD6	210	212	195	42					

Table 2: 2nd order interaction ranking between FXYD6 VS Individual members.

Conflict of interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

Author's contributions

Concept, design, in silico implementation - SS. Analysis and interpretation of results - SS. Manuscript writing - SS. Manuscript revision - SS. Approval of manuscript - SS

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES

Individual members w.r.t FXYD6

USH1C / VSIG2 / MCOLN3 / ST6GALNAC2 / CAPN6 ...
ABCB1 / PTHLH / NTSR1 / JPH1 / COBL / IL1RL1 ...
DHCR24 / TSPAN1 / PLPPR4 / MYRF / SOX9 / KLK10 ...
KLK8 / PRRG3 / STK26 / BICDL1 / PAK6 / GIPC2 ...
HECW2 / HERC5 / RASGEF1B / CDKL2 / EGF / KIAA1644 ...
PIANP / COL2A1 / SLAIN1 / MDGA2 / RNF157 / SLC47A1 ...
PRDM16 / SLC44A3 / CRABP2 / SUS4 / HHIPL2 ...
CCDC150 / IGSF11 / CCDC39 / PRSS35 / ASTN2 / GPHA2 ...
CDH8 / FAM124A / CCDC3 / ITIH2 / CACNA2D1 / SRSF12 ...
NCAM2 / SLC26A2 / CLIC2 / GRIP1 / SH3RF2 / STEAP2 ...
GRHL3 / NPM2 / CLIC6 / ACTC1 / ACE / SPON2 / CPAMD8 ...
CHRN2 / CYP3A4 / KIAA1522 / AKNAD1 / ARHGEF3 / SGMS2 ...
/ SLC9B2 / FAM160A1 / ANKRD33B / STEAP1 / ADCY1 / KDM1B ...
TRPV6 / AQP3 / PHYHIPL / PPP1R36 / CACNB2 / SPINT1 ...
SCN3B / USP54 / SERPINB8 / PLEKHA7 / ANPEP / MYO1A ...
SGSM1 / GPD1 / DNAAF3 / HRASLS5 / BDKRB2 / NSG1 / RAB3B ...
OTUD7A / DLGAP1 / CDC42BPG / ANO5 / CFAP46 / ANGPTL7 ...
ISG20 / MBOAT1 / TPSAB1 / SPTLC3 / BPGM / RCAN2 / RSPH9 ...
CES4A / PIFO / SLCO2A1 / SLC35G1 / MYO1D / FAM91A1 / KCNA2 ...
LRRN4CL / GPR4 / ERN1 / TMEM125 / WSCD1 / TMEM30B / SYNM ...
CAPN12 / RIPK4 / FAM162B / CCSER1 / BEX5 / OSBP2 / MAFF ...
TCN2 / PCLO / INSIG1 / NF2 / NCR3LG1 / FAM78B / FAT4 ...
SLC6A9 / LAMB3 / TPSB2 / ENPP1 / AFDN-DT / SH3BGRL2 ...
ANKRD35 / SREBF2 / COL15A1 / C9orf129

FXYD6

Table 3: 2nd order combinatorial hypotheses between FXYD6 and Individual members.

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Source of Data

Data used in this research work was released in a publication in Patel et al. [1]. Permission to use, granted by PNAS.

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